

Antibiotic Resistance and Plasmid Profile of Pathogenic Bacteria Isolated From Drinking Water in Oshimili South L.G.A. of Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

A total of 20 drinking water sources comprising; well-water, river water, borehole water, sachet water and bottled water were sampled from three towns (Asaba, Oko and Okwe) within Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The total viable bacterial and coliform counts determined by spread plate technique ranged from 1.6×10^2 to 9.4×10^4 cfu/ml and 1.2×10^2 to 9.1×10^4 cfu/ml respectively. Identification of isolates done using standard methods revealed the following; Escherichia species 57(10.9%), Bacillus species 56(10.8%), Salmonella species 55(10.6%), Staphylococcus species 51(9.8%), Pseudomonas species 50(9.6%), Shigella species 47(9.0%), Enterobacter species 40(7.7%), Proteus species 35(6.7%), Klebsiella species 32(6.2%), Corynebacterium species 30(5.7%), Enterococcus species 27(5.2%), Aeromonas species 25(46.8%) and Micrococcus species 13(2.5%). Antibiotic sensitivity showed that the isolates were most susceptible to ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin. About 86.27% of all the gram negative isolates were resistant to Amoxicillin and 82.35% were resistant to Streptomycin while 90.9% of all gram positive bacteria isolates were resistant to Tetracycline. The plasmid analysis carried out unraveled that the isolates; Klebsiella spp., Escherichia spp., Bacillus spp. and Proteus spp. had two bands of DNA with molecular weight ranging from 8,000bp to 10,000bp while Staphylococcus spp. had no visible band indicating that its resistance gene was integrated into the chromosome. Not all the borehole waters are safe for consumption and the well waters were of poorer bacteriological quality, indicating health risk to the inhabitants of the area. The danger of indiscriminate use of antibiotics by individuals should also be emphasized.

Keywords: Antibiotic, resistance, pathogens, isolates, plasmid profile.

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotics are antimicrobial agents produced by microorganisms, better described as any natural substance that can stop the development of several cell types (Todar, 2009). The majority of species that create antibiotics as secondary metabolites are soil-dwelling organisms, and the majority of these organisms produce spores or other types of dominating cells. Depending on how their selective toxicity works, antibiotics are either bacteriostatic or bactericidal. They may affect the bacterial cell's ribosome, cell membrane, or cell wall. Depending on the species of bacteria, those that affect the cell wall may include up to seven enzymes that bind the peptidoglycan unit via their D-alanyl-D-alanine residues. Penicillin-binding proteins are the name for enzymes that bind β -lactam antibiotics. (Adebayo-Tayo et al., 2012; Colodner et al., 2007). Nitrofurantoin, gentamycin, streptomycin, and neomycin are antibiotics that act on the 30S ribosomes, while chloramphenicol, lincomycin, clindamycin, erythromycin, and the inhibitor of metabolic pathways by competitive antagonism work on the 50S protein of the ribosome. (Doublet et al., 2003; Cheesbrough, 2006). Antibiotic resistance is the decrease in an antibiotic's ability to kill a bacterial cell. It can develop due to natural selection or mutation. (Hsu et al., 2007). Circular deoxyribonucleic acid molecules known as plasmids are found in some bacterial cells and allow for the transmission of resistance qualities from one related organism to another.

Water has the quality and property of being the universal solvent, which makes it a special material in the world. (Nelson, 2002). Water performs its biological purpose by allowing both organic and inorganic chemicals to dissolve in it, resulting in the numerous functions they perform within cells. Water makes up a sizeable portion of the human body's lymphatic system, blood, and other liquid-related organs and tissues. (Prasai et al., 2007). Through leaching and human activity, pathogens and dangerous chemicals enter the drinking water system and contaminate it. The health effects can be severe when such contaminated water is used for human consumption. Poor sanitation practices, such as situating on-site sanitation systems near wells, are undoubtedly a component in the contamination of the drinking water system. (Eni and Digha, 2004). The water from wells and boreholes will undoubtedly be contaminated if on-site sanitation facilities are located less than 50 meters from them, as has been established and acknowledged as a standard (Madu, and Otuokere, 2017). Dumping of waste in open sites encourages infiltration of accumulated organic and inorganic substances as water percolates through the waste. Subsequently, the contaminated water seeps through the soil into ground water including boreholes dug close to such sites which can also be contaminated by same process making it unfit for drinking (Aderemi et al., 2011; Ikem et al., 2011; Ejiogu et al., 2018).

Water-borne diseases are prominent in the developing countries and greater percentage of the population at risk are children (WHO, 2014). About 3.4million deaths of which 1.4million are children are recorded each year due to water related diseases (WHO, 2004; WHO, 2010). WHO in 2011 reported that mortality of water associated diseases exceeds 5million people per year and more than 50% is as a result of intestinal infection mostly due to outbreak of cholera. Hence, getting safe water for human consumption is essential for good health and a basic human right. Therefore, the quality of drinking water sources needs to be checked periodically in order to ascertain whether they are good for human consumption and other domestic use.

Asaba, Oko and Okwe communities in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State have a lot of wells, rivers, boreholes as well as sachet and bottled water companies to provide drinking water to curb the acute water shortages experienced by the inhabitants. These communities are low-lying coastal communities and within them are various improperly managed sanitation systems, including Ventilated Improved Pits (VIPs). In addition, the water table is quite high in the low-lying part of the areas. Thus the possibility of the local ground water system being contaminated by microorganisms from the various pits cannot be overlooked. These communities may experience periodic outbreaks of diseases like acute gastrointestinal disorders including; dysentery, cholera, etc. which may be due to drinking polluted water. It is therefore important to investigate the possibility or otherwise of pollution of the water sourced from these drinking water systems to ascertain whether the diseases which may be encountered by these communities are either directly or indirectly related to water sources. It is on this basis that this study is aimed at determining the antibiotic resistance and plasmid profile of bacterial pathogens isolated from drinking water in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

A total of 20 drinking water samples were collected by random sampling from different drinking water sources which included well-water, river water, borehole water, sachet and bottled water (with NAFDAC registration number) from three towns (Asaba, Oko and Okwe) in Oshimili South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The water samples were collected in sterile 1litre plastic containers and taken to the laboratory for analysis within 24 hours of collection.

Bacteriological Analysis

The media used in this study which included; Nutrient Agar, Nutrient broth, Salmonella-Shigella Agar, MacConkey Agar, Agarose powder were prepared according to the manufacturer's specifications.

Enumeration of aerobic heterotrophic bacteria was carried out using standard bacteriological spread plate method. Ten-fold serial dilution of each of the water samples was prepared aseptically in physiological saline to get 10^{-1} up to 10^{-4} dilutions. 0.1ml aliquot of each dilution was placed on Nutrient Agar, Salmonella-Shigella Agar and MacConkey Agar plates in triplicate. All incubations were conducted at 37°C for 24 hours under aerobic conditions and plates containing 30 to 300 colonies were selected and counted. The number of colony-forming units per ml (cfu/ml) was calculated by multiplying the number of colonies by the reciprocal of the dilution factor (Cheesbrough, 2005; Cheesbrough, 2006; Cheesbrough, 2008).

Representatives of each of the bacterial colony were sub-cultured by streaking onto nutrient agar plates for purification and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The isolated and purified bacterial strains were stored on agar slant at 4°C until needed for biochemical tests, sensitivity tests and plasmid analysis.

Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Typical colonies were identified using standard morphological and biochemical characteristics as described by (Jawetz et al., 1989; Cheesbrough, 2005; Cheesbrough, 2006; Cheesbrough, 2008).

Antibiotic Sensitivity Testing

The agar diffusion technique as described by Bauer et al. (1996) was used. Using a sterile loop, an inoculum was picked from the surface of each selected colony and transferred into a sterile test tube containing 5ml of nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. A loopfull of bacterial suspension was streaked on the surface of Nutrient Agar. The appropriate multi-disc depending on whether the test organism plated was a Gram negative or Gram positive organism was then placed firmly onto the surface of the dried plates, using sterile forceps. The plates were left at room temperature for one hour to allow diffusion of the different antibiotics from the disc into the medium and then incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours. Interpretation of results was done using the zone sizes. Zone of inhibition of greater than 18mm were considered sensitive, 15-17mm were considered moderately sensitive and below 15mm or no zone of inhibition were considered resistant.

Plasmid Analysis

Isolates selected for plasmid analysis were sub-cultured into nutrient broth bottles and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. They included isolates from;

- Sample B2: Klebsiella spp. (borehole water from Okwe),
- Sample D2: Escherichia spp. (stream water from Oko),
- Sample E1: Bacillus spp. (well water from Asaba),
- Sample F1: Staphylococcus spp. (borehole water from Asaba) and
- Sample B21: Proteus spp. (borehole water from Okwe).

The method described by Robins-Browne et al. (2004) for plasmid extraction and profiling was adopted in this study. 1.5ml of overnight nutrient broth culture of each of the selected isolates was spun for 1 minute in a micro-centrifuge to pellet cells. The supernatant was gently decanted leaving 50-100µl together with cell pellet and vortex at high speed to re-suspend cell. A 300µl of TENs was added and mixed by inverting tubes 3-5 times until the mixture becomes sticky. 150µl of 3.0M sodium acetate (pH 5.2) was then added to the preparation, followed by vortex mixing. The preparation was spun for 5 minutes in a micro-centrifuge to pellet cell debris and chromosomal DNA. The supernatant was transferred into a fresh test tube and mixed well with 900µl of ice-cold absolute ethanol, spun again for 10 minutes to pellet plasmid DNA (white pellet was observed). The supernatant was discarded; the pellet was rinsed twice with 1ml of 70% ethanol and dried twice for 10 minutes. The pellet was re-suspended in 20-40µl of Te buffer for further use. 100ml of 1x TBE buffer was added to 0.8g of agarose powder and dissolved by boiling/heating for 3-5 minutes using a magnetic sterile water bath. It was allowed to cool to 50°C and 10µl of ethidium bromide added, gently mixed by swirling and then poured into electrophoresis tank with comb in place to obtain a gel thickness of about 4.5mm. It was allowed to stand for 20 minutes to polymerize/solidify. The comb was removed; the tray placed in the electrophoresis tank and 1x TBE buffer poured into the tank to ensure the buffer covers the surface of the gel. 15-20µl of the sample was mixed with 2µl of the loading dye, the samples were carefully loaded into the wells with marker (standard) in lane 1 followed by the control. The electrodes were connected to the power pack with the negative terminal at the well side where the samples were loaded. The electrophoresis was run at 60-100v until the loading dye migrates to the end or about three quarter of the gel field. The electrode disconnected and the gel observed by UV-transilluminator.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained for the different parameters were subjected to statistical analysis using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) technique and the least significance difference (LSD) test was used to compare the means (Steel *et al.*, 1997).

RESULT

Enumeration of bacteria from different water sources (cfu/ml)

The result of enumeration of total aerobic bacterial and coliform counts presented in table 1 shows that water samples from Oko stream batch two has the highest total bacterial count (9.4×10^4 cfu/ml). This was followed by water samples from Asaba well batch one (3.0×10^4 cfu/ml), Okwe borehole batch one (7.4×10^3 cfu/ml) and Asaba borehole batch one (6.2×10^3 cfu/ml) while Asaba well batch two had the lowest count of 1.6×10^2 cfu/ml. Coliform count was highest in Oko stream batch two (9.1×10^4 cfu/ml), followed by Asaba well batch one (8.3×10^3 cfu/ml). While the lowest coliform count was recorded in Asaba bottled water batch two (2.9×10 cfu/ml).

Table 1: Enumeration of bacteria from different water sources (cfu/ml)

Sample code	Total bacterial count	Total coliform count
A1	4.1 x 10 ³	1.3 x 10 ³
B1	7.4 x 10 ³	9.7 x 10 ²
B2	1.9 x 10 ³	4.6 x 10 ²
C1	6.2 x 10 ³	1.6 x 10 ²
C2	3.7 x 10 ²	1.3 x 10 ²
D1	4.9 x 10 ²	5.0 x 10
D2	9.4 x 10 ⁴	9.1 x 10 ⁴
E1	3.0 x 10 ⁴	8.3 x 10 ³
E2	1.2 x 10 ³	1.9 x 10 ²
F1	1.7 x 10 ²	3.7 x 10
F2	1.9 x 10 ²	2.9 x 10
H1	2.5 x 10 ²	2.2 x 10 ²
H2	2.1 x 10 ²	1.7 x 10 ²
I1	1.6 x 10 ²	1.2 x 10 ²

Key: cfu/ml=colony forming unit per milliliter, **A1**=Oko borehole (batch one), **B1**=Okwe borehole (batch one), **B2**=Okwe borehole (batch two), **C2**=Asaba borehole (batch two), **D1**=Oko stream (batch one), **D2**=Oko stream (batch two), **E1**=Asaba well (batch one), **E2**=Asaba well (batch two), **F1**=Asaba bottled water (batch one), **F2**=Asaba bottled water (batch two), **H1** – Oko well (batch one), **H2** – Oko well (batch two), **I1** – Okwe well (batch one).

Table 2 revealed the biochemical characteristics of the bacterial isolates from drinking water samples in Oshimili South L.G.A of Delta State to include thirteen genera, namely; Enterobacter spp., Pseudomonas spp., Klebsiella spp., Bacillus spp., Staphylococcus spp., Proteus spp., Aeromonas spp., Corynebacterium spp., Escherichia spp., Micrococcus spp., Staphylococcus spp., Enterococcus spp., Salmonella spp. and Shigella spp.

Table 2: Characteristics of bacterial isolates

Sample	Cell Shape	Gram rxn	VP	Catalase	H ₂ S	Coagulase	Oxidase	Urease	Citrate	MR	Indole	Glucose	Lactose	Probable bacteria
1	R	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	Enterobacter spp.
2	R	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	Pseudomonas spp.
3	R	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	Klebsiella spp.
4	R	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	Bacillus spp.
5	R	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	Proteus spp.
6	R	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	Aeromonas spp.

7	R	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	Corynebacterium spp.
8	R	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	Escherichia spp.
9	C	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	Micrococcus spp.
10	C	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	Staphylococcus spp.
11	C	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	Enterococcus spp.
12	R	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	Salmonella spp.
13	R	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Shigella spp.

Key: VP=Voges Proskauer, MR=Methyl Red, H₂S=Hydrogen Sulphide, R=Rod, C=Cocci, +=Positive, -=Negative, spp.=Species

Table 3 below represented the percentage frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates in drinking water samples collected from different locations in Oshimili South L.G.A of Delta State. Escherichia spp. was the most occurring bacteria isolate with occurrence rate of 57 (10.9%) closely followed by Bacillus spp. with 56 (10.8%) while the least bacteria isolate was Micrococcus spp. with occurring rate of 13 (2.5%).

Table 3: Percentage occurrence of each isolate in the water samples

Isolate	No. of occurrence	Frequency (%)
Enterobacter spp.	40	7.7
Pseudomonas spp.	50	9.6
Klebsiella spp.	32	6.2
Proteus spp.	35	6.7
Bacillus spp.	56	10.8
Aeromonas spp.	25	4.8
Corynebacteriu spp.m	30	5.7
Escherichia spp.	57	10.9
Micrococcus spp.	13	2.5
Staphylococcus spp.	51	9.8
Enterococcus spp.	27	5.2
Salmonella spp.	55	10.6
Shigella spp.	47	9.0
Total	520	100

The percentage resistance of gram negative isolates to antibiotics is presented below in Table 4. The result unraveled that the organisms were most sensitive to Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin antibiotics while most resistant to Streptomycin, Amoxicillin and Pefloxacin. The gram positive isolates were most sensitive to Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone antibiotics but were resistance to Streptomycin, Ampiclox and Tetracycline as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 6 shows that 86.27% of all gram negative isolates were resistant to Amoxicillin, 82.35% were resistant to Streptomycin, 74.50% were resistant to Perfloxacin and 72.54% were resistant to Chloramphenicol with the lowest

percentage resistance of 21.57% to Gentamycin and 25.49% to Ciprofloxacin. However, table 7 revealed that 90.9% and 81.8% of all gram positive isolates were resistant to Tetracycline and Ampiclox respectively; while they had lowest percentage resistance of 9.1% and 18.2% to Ciprofloxacin and Ceftriaxone respectively.

Table 4: Percentage resistance of gram negative isolates to antibiotics

Isolates	No. of Isolates	SXT n(%)	CH n(%)	SP n(%)	CPX n(%)	AM n(%)	AU n(%)	CN n(%)	PEF n(%)	OFX n(%)	S n(%)
Enterobacter spp.	5	3(60)	3(60)	2(40)	0(0)	3(60)	2(40)	1(20)	2(40)	0(0)	3(60)
Pseudomonas spp.	8	6(75)	5(63)	6(75)	1(13)	5(63)	5(63)	2(25)	4(50)	3(38)	6(75)
Klebsiella spp.	12	10(83)	9(75)	6(50)	1(8)	12(100)	11(92)	1(8)	10(83)	1(8)	10(83)
Proteus spp.	3	1(33)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	1(33)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	2(66)
Aeromonas spp.	5	5(100)	5(100)	0(0)	0(0)	5(100)	2(40)	0(0)	3(60)	0(0)	5(100)
Salmonella spp.	8	2(25)	6(75)	8(100)	6(75)	7(86)	5(63)	4(50)	8(100)	5(63)	6(75)
Shigella spp.	5	4(80)	2(40)	5(100)	4(80)	4(80)	3(60)	0(0)	5(100)	5(100)	4(80)
Escherichia spp.	5	3(60)	3(60)	2(40)	0(0)	5(100)	0(0)	5(100)	0(0)	0(0)	5(100)

KEY:PEF=Pefloxacin,CH=Chloramphenicol, CN=Gentamycin,CPX=Ciprofloxacin,S=Streptomycin,AM=Amoxicillin,SP=Sparfloxacin,AU=Augmentin, OFX=Ofloxacin, SXT=Septin.

Table 5: Percentage of antibiotics resistance of gram positive isolates

Isolates	No. of isolates	PEF n(%)	CN n(%)	APX n(%)	CF n(%)	AM n(%)	R n(%)	CPX n(%)	S n(%)	TET n(%)	E n(%)
Staphylococcuspp.	3	1(33)	0(0)	2(66)	1(33)	1(33)	1(33)	0(0)	2(66)	3(100)	2(66)
Bacilluspp.	4	3(75)	1(25)	3(75)	1(25)	2(50)	2(50)	0(0)	3(75)	3(75)	2(50)
Micrococcuspp.	4	2(50)	3(75)	4(100)	0(0)	4(100)	3(75)	0(0)	4(100)	3(75)	2(50)

KEY: PEF=Pefloxacin, CN=Gentamycin, APX=Ampiclox, CF=Ceftriaxone, CPX=Ciprofloxacin, S=Streptomycin, TET=Tetracycline, E=Erythromycin, AM=Amoxicillin, R=Rocephin.

Table 6: Percentage resistance profile of antibiotics against gram negative isolates

Antibiotics	No. of resistance	Frequency (%)
SXT	35	68.63
CH	37	72.54
SP	33	64.71
CPX	13	25.49

AM	44	86.27
AU	36	70.58
CN	11	21.57
PEF	38	74.50
OFX	13	25.49
S	42	82.35

KEY:PEF=Pefloxacin, AM=Amoxicillin, AU=Augmentin, CPX=Ciprofloxacin, S=Streptomycin, CN Gentamycin, OFX=Ofloxacin, CH=Chloramphenicol, SP=Sparfloxacin, SXT=Septrin.

Table 7: Percentage resistance profile of antibiotics against gram positive isolates

Antibiotics	No. of resistance	Frequency (%)
PEF	8	72.7
CN	5	45.5
APX	9	81.8
CF	2	18.2
AM	7	63.6
R	6	54.5
CPX	1	9.1
S	7	63.6
TET	10	90.9
E	5	45.4

KEY: PEF=Pefloxacin, CN=Gentamycin, APX=Ampiclox, CF=Ceftriaxone, CPX=Ciprofloxacin, S=Streptomycin, TET=Tetracycline, E=Erythromycin, AM=Amoxicillin, R=Rocephin.

The result of the plasmid analysis carried out showed in Fig. 1(the plasmid band)below that isolates in lane 1, 2, 3 and 5 (Klebsiellaspp., Escherichiaspp., Bacillus spp. Proteusspp.) had two bands of DNA with molecular weight ranging from 8,000bp to 10,000bp while the isolate in lane 4 (Staphylococcus spp.) had no visible band.

Fig.1: The Plasmid Band (Lane 1 Klebsiella spp., Lane 2 Escherichia spp., Lane 3 Bacillus spp., Lane 4 Staphylococcus spp. and Lane 5 Proteus spp.)

DISCUSSION

This study revealed the presence of heterotrophic and coliform bacteria in the water samples analyzed. The highest heterotrophic bacteria count obtained was 9.4×10^4 cfu/ml while the least heterotrophic bacteria count was 1.6×10^2 cfu/ml. The coliform bacteria count of 9.1×10^4 cfu/ml was recorded as the highest in this study. FAO (2005) stated that bacteria counts that is greater than or equal to 10^6 cells/ml and enterobacteriaceae counts greater than or equal to 10^5 cells/ml are dangerous and could result to some health problems like food poisoning and intoxication. From the results obtained, the values of bacteria count was less than the above stated dose values that will cause or pose serious health risk, but that notwithstanding, the range of counts obtained from this study is high for water samples meant for human consumption (De-Zuane, 1997; Dawson and Sartory, 2000). The total viable counts of microbes in a water sample reflect not only the handling history, but also the sanitary or hygienic quality of the water. It also reflects the sanitary level exercised or maintained in their production, transport and storage of drinking water (Baro et al., 2007).

In this present study, a total of thirteen (13) different bacteria were isolated and they include; *Enterobacter* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., *Proteus* spp., *Aeromonas* spp., *Corynebacterium* spp., *Escherichia* spp., *Micrococcus* spp., *Enterococcus* spp., *Salmonella* spp. and *Shigella* spp. This result is in agreement with previous research work (Edema et al., 2001; Itah and Akpan, 2005; Obi and Okocha, 2007; Ojo et al., 2007; Okonkwo et al., 2008) that isolated different genera of bacteria including; *Staphylococcus* spp., *Escherichia* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., and *Enterococcus* spp. from portable water. Among the bacteria isolated, a well-defined pathogen and indicator of faecal contamination of water samples found to be present in some water samples studied is the *Escherichia* spp. Its presence is an indication of the presence of other enteric pathogens such as *Salmonella typhi* and *Shigella dysenteriae*. Moreover, *Escherichia* spp. is known to cause many enteric diseases such as traveler's diarrhea and other forms of diarrhea (Sloat and Ziel, 1991; Prescott et al., 2002). In addition, opportunistic pathogens; *Klebsiella* spp. and *Proteus* spp. were identified and could cause nosocomial infections (hospital acquired infection). Typical examples of such infections and their causative agents are lower respiratory infection (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*), gastroenteritis (*E. coli*). Water from boreholes, streams and other sources may look clean and have no undesirable odour or taste. However, it is unfortunate that pathogens found in these water sources can be harmful by causing serious illnesses. In this study, bottle water samples had the lowest bacteria count which may be due to good processing methods such as filtration, chemical treatment and proper packaging. Water sample from boreholes also had low bacteria count which may be due to the depth of the boreholes. In some cases where the borehole water samples were grossly contaminated could be as a result of improper construction of boreholes, nature of pipes used, proximity to toilet facilities and various human activities around the borehole. Well and stream water could also be contaminated due to shallowness, animal waste, closeness of refuse dump sites, proximity to toilet facilities (closeness to latrines), improper placement of well covers, using different drawing bowls and plunging of bowls/bucket directly from the soil into the well as well as human activities around it (Dzuiban et al., 2006).

The prevalence of bacteria isolated from this study revealed that *Escherichia* spp. was the most occurring bacteria isolate with occurrence rate of 60(10.9%), while *Micrococcus* spp. was the least occurring bacteria with occurrence rate of 13(2.5%).

The total coliform for samples examined during this study were exceedingly high when compared to regulatory standards. The Environmental Protection Agency standard for presence of coliform bacteria in drinking water is zero/100ml (Environmental Protection Agency, 2002). The high coliform count obtained in the samples may be an indication that the water sources were faecally contaminated (Environmental Protection Agency, 2002; Osunide and Enezie, 2009). None of the River water samples in this study complied with the Environmental Protection Agency standard for coliforms in water. The presence of organisms like *Salmonella* spp., *Enterobacter* spp. and *Enterococcus* spp. signifies contamination of water from some domestic sources. The presence of *Staphylococcus* spp. also reveals a low level of hygiene which is medically unsafe especially infections caused by coliforms or *Staphylococcus* spp. The *Staphylococcus* spp. enterotoxin responsible for water borne diseases is heat stable and infective dose is almost $10^7 - 10^8$ cells per gram of the food (Uriah, 2004). The total count produced a means of assuring the conditions obtained when portable water is prepared in the industry, it is recognized that an improvement in cleanliness of equipment reduces the level of contaminants found in portable water especially with organism which grow at 20-30°C and water can be an important source of such contaminants (Schlegel, 2002; Onifade and Ilori, 2008).

The presence of *Salmonella* species in the water samples corroborates with the studies of Liuet al. (2018) who reported the presence and persistence of *Salmonella* in water samples. The contamination level of bacteria obtained in this study can be associated with the storage environment and the physiology of the contaminating bacterial genera. Water has been listed as one of the sources of microbes. Thus the level of bacteria recovered may indicate a potential hazard to

the human. The high occurrence of bacterial species is of public health concern because this may indicate obvious health hazard in terms of direct consumption of bacteriological contaminated water (Frazier and Westhoff, 2008).

The source of these organisms may vary extensively. While bacterial genera may have originated from illegal dumping of waste in water environment, effluent discharged directly into water bodies as reported by Hunter et al. (2001) who stated that handling and other water processing equipment may be amongst the primary sources of contamination of drinking water. Most of the bacteria species have been isolated from drinking water and the physiological adaptation of these bacteria genera may have supported their survival (Miller and Pegues, 2000). Salmonella species are capable of producing acute and chronic infections which can affect animals and humans (Itah and Akpan, 2005).

A high level drug resistance was noted against ampiclox, tetracycline, streptomycin and amoxicillin. This may be attributed to the excessive use of antibiotics in clinical practice, especially in asymptomatic patients (Adebayo et al., 2012). Multidrug resistance in Salmonella species have been attributed to prior treatment with antimicrobials and is a proven risk factor as reported earlier in previous studies. Resistance to amoxicillin is on the rise as is the case with this study. Infections by resistant bacterial strains are possibly better treated by the synergistic action of 2 antimicrobials as has been reported in earlier studies (Halawani and Shohayeb, 2008).

The results of the overall sensitivity patterns show that there is a mild difference in the sensitivity pattern of present study and earlier reports (Adebayo et al., 2012; Hsu et al., 2007). This indicates that the sensitivity pattern changes from the various water environments. It also indicates the importance of study of sensitivity, as emphasized by various international authorities that every water factory should have its individual antibiotic sensitivity pattern since the standard antibiotic sensitivity pattern may not hold true for every area (Madigan et al., 2000).

Ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin and sparfloxacin in this study have proved to be effective drugs as previously reported by Halawani and Shohayeb (2008). Colodner et al. (2007) have found better activity of ciprofloxacin, ofloxacin and sparfloxacin against bacterial isolates from water samples. From this present study, it is evident that there is distinct difference in the sensitivity pattern of bacterial isolates from specimen to specimen. The result of the plasmid analysis carried out showed in Fig.1 unraveled that the isolates; Klebsiella spp., Escherichia spp., Bacillus spp. and Proteus spp. had two bands of DNA with molecular weight ranging from 8,000bp to 10,000bp while Staphylococcus spp. had no visible band indicating that the isolate being also resistant possibly had its resistance gene integrated into the chromosome (Depardieu et al., 2007; Ehiagheet al., 2013).

In order to avoid development of resistance, careful monitoring of antibiotic use and bacterial susceptibility is recommended. Antibiotic resistance patterns have been used to differentiate strains involved in outbreaks as antimicrobial susceptibility testing is important in detecting new resistant phenotypes although it lacks specificity.

CONCLUSION

This investigation revealed that some borehole waters in Oshimili South Local Government Area in Delta State are not safe for consumption. The well waters were of poorer bacteriological qualities indicative of health risk to the inhabitants of the geographical location. Hence, sites of boreholes and wells are very important as clean and hygienic environment promote safety of water. The results of sensitivity of bacterial isolates indicated that multiple antibiotic resistant bacteria are major clinical problem. Therefore, the construction pit latrines near water sources should be avoided and the danger of indiscriminate use of antibiotics by individuals and the general public should also be emphasized.

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